

EVIDENCE OF CARBOXY ESTER MECHANISMS
IN NITRIFICATION FROM THE DYNAMIC
REACTION KINETICS AT NATURAL
CONCENTRATIONS.

Part I. Chi-square Probability Testing of Common Rate
Equations for the Oxidation of Ammonia in RAS
Nitrification Biofilters, in which the Role of Liquid Film
Diffusion is accounted for, Supports Multiple Molecule
Reaction Mechanisms.

Andrew P. G. Newton¹

¹) newton.carboxy.ester@gmail.com

Abstract

Kinetic data from two submerged nitrifying filters in parallel used for maintaining the water quality in an experimental recycle smolt hatchery system is examined. The filter inlet total ammonia nitrogen concentrations recorded were up to 0.32 mg/l and correspond to those occurring in natural watercourses with superficial residence times ranging from 3 to 45 minutes. The smolts received a constant daily amount of nitrogen in their feed resulting in a constant ammonia load in the closed system. In addition to the system perturbations from feeding, further perturbations were introduced by altering the flowrate through the filters once every 24 hours. With the oxygen levels not limiting the reaction and with a constant pH the ammonia oxidation rate would be expected to be a function of the ammonia concentration alone. Excellent chi-square probability fits are found with liquid film diffusion limitations, however at much reduced rates from those anticipated. When comparing the rate constants of each of the two filters, half order kinetics is supported. Michaelis-Menten kinetics or the biological rate equation that accounts for internal diffusion are also supported, but only with significant differences in the number of enzyme sites in each filter. The use of an activator may well then be involved, but this contradicts literature mechanisms.

Key words: Nitrification, Biofilters, Reaction kinetics, Liquid film diffusion, Operational recycle aquaculture system

1. Introduction

Nitrification is one of the main biological processes in the nitrogen cycle and interpretation and collation of experimental data is of practical importance. The challenge may range from understanding nitrification performance in a municipal water treatment process, in fertilized soils, in aquaculture or its role in environmental chemistry. In all these cases accurate kinetic models and a thorough understanding of the processes are required. This work evaluates and interprets data from submerged nitrification filters, whereby the flowrate through the filters was adjusted every 24 hours, a form of step testing. The results of such testing, in conjunction with rigorous statistical analysis, yields insights into the kinetics and reaction mechanisms of nitrification. Biological processes are complicated, but there are evolutionary requirements on these processes.

Smolt hatchery systems, unlike most water treatment processes, experience very low BOD loadings. The substrate concentrations are also very low in comparison to water treatment plants and are more in line with those found in natural water courses. In a recycle smolt hatchery system the waste water from rearing the smolts first undergoes sedimentation to remove the suspended solids. This is then followed by biological treatment in which ammonia, whereby it is ammonia gas that is more toxic, is said to be oxidised by nitrifying bacteria via nitrite. Nitrite is also very toxic to the fish compared to the relatively non-toxic nitrate. Thus a recycle system demands effective removal of ammonia and nitrites down to very low concentrations. In the case of salmonid smolts the optimal ammonium ion concentrations are below 0.4 mg/l $\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$ with desirable levels of 1 mg/l for $\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$ or 0.005 $\text{NH}_3(\text{g}) - \text{N}$ mg/l for ammonia gas [1]. Scheduled feeding and the subsequent excretion result in a dynamic system, giving rise to cyclic disturbances in the ammonia production rate. Such disturbances are generally easily taken care of by nitrifying filters, thus preventing significant smolt mortality.

Explain road map...In subsequent papers, the bacteria's response to disturbances is examined in more detail.

Nitrification was once thought to be carried out almost exclusively by two distinct genera of autotrophic bacteria. The first genus, which has the prefix Nitroso- (e.g. *Nitrosomonas europaea*), oxidises ammonia to nitrite. The second genus, whose prefix is Nitro- (e.g. *Nitrobacter europaea*), then oxidises the nitrite to nitrate. It has relatively recently been established [2] that in fact archaea rather than bacteria predominate in the environments that have been examined. The traditional nitrifying bacteria term is being used to detail both the archaea and bacteria present.

The oxidation of ammonia to nitrite has the overall stoichiometry:

The estimated energy released is between 244 and 353 kJ/mol [3]. The nitrification reactions thus afford little energy and the bacteria grow very slowly.

Skinner and Walker [4] reported a minimal doubling time at 30°C of 8 hours in batch culture and 11 hours for continuous culture. Like a chemical process plant the bacteria require good process control and optimisation. The control and optimisation problem can be split into three time horizons: immediate control of the process required to respond to disturbances, dynamic optimisation of the process once at steady state to maximise the energy won and thirdly the longer strategic considerations. A strategy might be as to whether the bacteria should multiply or increase their energy reserves (inventory). It might be thought that the nitrifying reactions are in competition with that of faster growing heterotrophic bacteria who need fixed nitrogen to make amino acids.

1.1. Mechanisms, Stoichiometry and Sources of Oxygen

The hypothesised reaction mechanism and the observed reaction kinetics should be consistent. The oxidation of ammonia to nitrite involves passing through many oxidation states. In 1926 Kluver and Donker [5] hypothesised, based upon a catalytic-hydrogen-transfer theory, the following mechanisms:

Hydroxylamine is indicated as the first intermediate with nitroxyl as the second. That biological reactions are driven by the transfer of electrons along cytochrome chains rather than "hydrogen transfer" which was proposed at that time.

Adding hydroxylamine, a mutagen, to *Nitrosomonas* cultures causes severe inhibition. In 1952 Lees [6] found that hydroxylamine amounts less than 1.5 mg/l nitrogen were oxidised to nitrite and that it was oxidised a good deal faster than ammonia at pH's lower than 8.4. Hydrazine inhibits nitrification halting nitrite formation. Hofman and Lees [7] then established that upon the addition of small amounts of hydrazine small amounts of hydroxylamine arise. They claimed that this was evidence that the "oxidation of ammonia to nitrite proceeds via hydroxylamine". The priority is that hydrazine competitively binds to active enzyme sites for the oxidation of hydroxylamine. Which is then deemed to result in the accumulation of hydroxylamine thus allowing its detection.

A three step mechanism, each involving two electrons, was retained by Hofman and Lees [7] and others [8] [9] [10].

Postulated intermediates such as hyponitrite ($\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^{2-}$), dihydroxyammonia ($\text{NH}(\text{OH})_2$), nitroxyl (HNO) and nitrohydroxylamine were never detected [11]

and this despite ever improving detection methods. Having refined the specificity of the test methods of Hofman and Lees, Yoshida and Alexander [12] found that hydroxylamine was only evident in the presence of hydrazine. They cautioned that, "the demonstration that hydroxylamine is produced during nitrification does not indicate that hydroxylamine is on the direct pathway of nitrogen oxidation by the bacterium". Through further experiments [13] and by conducting a nitrogen balance they suggested that the "hydroxylamine is converted enzymatically to a compound which decomposes spontaneously to yield nitrous oxide". Hollocher et al. [14] conducted experiments with ammonia and hydrazine using ^{15}N and $^{18}\text{O}_2$ to form an oxime, whereby they established that the hydroxylamine formed originated from ammonia and not hydrazine. Andersson and Hooper [15] determined via isotope experiments that one oxygen is added to ammonia from O_2 , "assuming hydroxylamine is, indeed, an intermediate", with the other coming from water. Ammonia is thus oxidised by a peroxide building enzyme, which is speculated to be a copper-based enzyme [16][17], and such reactions are irreversible. The intermediate product then travels to the second separate enzyme. This second step is then a hydrolysis reaction, which are generally reversible. Although hydroxylamine is commonly given as the first intermediate, it has never been observed or trapped as an oxime during the normal oxidation of ammonia in which hydrazine is absent. Similarly the detailed mechanisms of denitrification, which are closely related to those of nitrification, remain poorly understood [18].

Both free ammonia and ammonium ions are given as the substrate for the monooxygenase enzyme with hydroxylamine as the reaction product (first reaction intermediate). The reaction stoichiometry, shown here for ammonia gas as substrate [17], then becomes:-

The second enzyme, released on breakage of the cells, performs the hydrolysis reaction [15] to yield nitrite. With hydroxylamine as the substrate, the stoichiometry (it is here that a second intermediate, following the transfer of two electrons, would be expected in the mechanism) for the enzyme thus named hydroxylamine oxidoreductase becomes:-

It should be noted that the enzyme is not found [19] in the archaea *Nitrososphaerota maritimus*. In addition to the above, much work has been undertaken into the oxidation/reduction potentials of hydroxylamine and nitrite, in purifying and determining spectra of cytochromes as well as determining genomes [20]. This series of papers examines more the primary substrates involved and low energy (ATP) utilization issues rather than the high energy electron transfer chain.

2. Experimental

The kinetic data came from an experimental smolt hatchery system operating in total recycle. As part of growth studies, the smolts received a fixed amount of feed daily with a fixed nitrogen content. The smolt holding densities were very low to reduce stress. The setup consisted of several small rearing tanks draining into a very large sedimentation basin with the system design based upon chemical engineering unit operation principles. The water was then pumped through two filters (R1 and R2) in parallel, to test two different designs, and into a header tank which gravity fed the rearing tanks. The temperature was controlled to $15 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and the buffering capacity of the system held the pH at 7.2 ± 0.1 . Water samples were taken each morning, before and after the two filters. The flowrate was then altered and left for 24 hours.

Each filter was made from two sections of 6 inch dark grey plastic piping in series. The filters differed in that R2 had conical entrances and exits. Each section, see Fig. 1, was around 2 meters in length and filled with sieved limestone granulate 1.2 cm in diameter. The ends contained pieces of $1\frac{3}{4}$ inch plastic rashig rings. In examining the kinetics the area and volume of the ends were ignored in the analysis. The ratio of particle diameter to filter diameter was low in order to avoid the nitrification filters being blocked with biomass.

3. Results

The kinetic data consists of 39 statistically independent points per filter where the flowrate to each filter was not the same. The points covered a wide range of ammonia-N concentrations by aquatic standards. The total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) influent concentration varied from 0.322 to 0.019 mg/l and the effluent concentration from 0.111 to 0.006 mg/l. The flowrates measured, using rotameters, were varied between 1.3 l/min and 19 l/min. The ammonia determinations were carried out on a routine basis as part of other long term studies. The uncertainties to the sodium nitroprusside [21] based method were determined from standards in the ranges experienced. No data points were dropped from the analysis.

Lower flowrates resulted in higher inlet TAN concentrations with the outlet TAN concentration remaining low. On top of this behaviour is the disturbances to the system caused by the fish themselves from feeding. Figure 2 illustrates the data spread.

The oxidation of ammonia according to Eqn. (5) involves ammonia and a peroxide, forming hydroxylamine. The inlet dissolved oxygen concentration (over 7 ppm) always exceeded the stoichiometric requirement by many orders of magnitude and consequently the dissolved oxygen concentration is not a factor in the observed rate of reaction. [10][22][23].

3.1. Rate Equations

The mechanisms for the oxidation of ammonia in excess oxygen implies rate equations involving the concentration of ammonia only. For plug flow the residence time is given by:

Dimensions in cm
Ends contain 80 pieces of 1/4" plastic rashig rings

Figure 1: Filter Dimensions

$$\tau = \frac{1}{a_w} \int_{C_{in}}^{C_{out}} \frac{dC}{N} \quad (7)$$

Some simple rate equations are easy to test for as they have analytical solutions, whereby the data can be plotted to give the rate constants. As the concentrations are very low the reaction order might be assumed to be first order. Biological reactions are also often described as following Michaelis-Menten kinetics where the substrate binds in equilibrium to an enzyme site followed by the reaction to the product. This is equivalent to saturation kinetics for chemical catalysts where the reactant binds to the limited number of active sites and then undergoes a reaction to form the product.

The plots given in Fig. 3 for first order kinetics offer no good fit to the data even if readings at lower flowrates are dropped from the analysis. Half order kinetics, as in Fig. 4, are not linear either. Michaelis-Menten kinetic plots are also similarly poor as given in Fig. 5, but a trend can be identified when the data is grouped for similar flowrates. This is illustrated for the two filters in Fig. 6. A linear relationship can be determined for a particular flowrate, but the intercept can be incorrectly positive. Thus the plots indicate that there is a flowrate component involved in the kinetics rather than a validation of Michaelis-Menten kinetics. The apparent Michaelis-Menten constants for the grouped flowrate data are listed in table 1.

The first order plots for the grouped flowrates show large differences in the natural log of the concentration ratios. This implies that there is a significant variation in the reaction rate even for similar flowrates. The reaction rates are

Figure 2: Inlet and Outlet Total Ammonia Nitrogen Concentrations

thus either being altered, say by an activator to optimise the process, or a result of the experimental uncertainties. The kinetic data was thus examined with statistical rigour involving all the rate equations for a single substrate (ammonia). In addition equations postulated by other authors were tested along with the equation derived from substrate inhibition mechanisms, although substrate inhibition has never been reported at the concentrations of ammonia studied here. Sigmoidal binding behaviour was also tested for. A selection of the rate equations tested are given in Table 2.

Figure 3: First Order Kinetics Plot

R1			R2		
Re	$k_I a_w$	k_{II}	Re	$k_I a_w$	k_{II}
137	0.271	14.68	155	0.189	-3.29
103	0.159	2.76	93	0.209	0.89
			85	0.154	-2.45
			75	0.139	-0.05
29	0.082	1.48	28	0.1	0.93
16	0.022	-4.34	13	0.048	-2.61

Table 1: Apparent Michaelis-Menten Kinetics constants

Figure 4: Half Order Kinetics Plot

Figure 5: Michaelis-Menten Kinetics

Figure 6: Michaelis-Menten Grouped R1: $q = 1.6$ (—), 2.9 (·····), 10.5 (---) and 14 (-·-·-) l/min R2: $q = 1.3, 2.8, 9.5, 15.6, 7.6$ and 8.7 l/min

Eqn	Kinetics	Equation	Integrated Equation
A	First Order	$N = k_1 a_w C$	$\ln\left(\frac{C_{in}}{C_{out}}\right) = k_1 a_w \tau$
B	Michaelis-Menten / Monod / Saturation	$N = \frac{k_1 a_w C}{1 + k_2 C}$	$\frac{1}{(C_{in} - C_{out})} \ln\left(\frac{C_{in}}{C_{out}}\right) = k_1 a_w \frac{\tau}{(C_{in} - C_{out})} - k_2 \tau$
C	Complete BRE $\lambda = \text{fn}(k_2 L, C^*)$	$N = \lambda \frac{k_1 a_w C}{1 + k_3 C}$	[24] Internal diffusion
D	Substrate Inhibition	$N = \frac{k_1 a_w C}{k_2 + C + C^2/k_3}$	
E	Sigmoidal	$N = \frac{k_1 a_w C^n}{1 + k_2 C^n}$	
F	1.2 Order	$N = k_1 a_w C^{1.2}$	[25] $C_{out}^{-0.2} - C_{in}^{-0.2} = 0.2 k_1 a_w \tau$
G	Zero Order	$N = k_1 a_w$	No film diffusion limitation
H	Half Order	$N = k_1 a_w C^{0.5}$	$\sqrt{C_{in}} - \sqrt{C_{out}} = 1/2 k_1 a_w \tau$
I	Second Order	$N = k_1 a_w C^2$	$1/C_{out} - 1/C_{in} = k_1 a_w \tau$

Table 2: Selection of Rate Equations Tested

The rate equations were numerically integrated using a Romberg routine to obtain the calculated residence times as in Eqn. 7. Determination of the kinetic parameters (rate and equilibrium constants) is insufficient, a statistical measure of association is required. The chi-square probability, Q, was calculated to this end.

$$\chi^2 \equiv \sum_{i=1}^p \left(\frac{\tau_i - \tau(C; k_1 \dots k_3)}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

where

$$\sigma_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p \left(\left(\frac{\partial \tau_i}{\partial C_{in_i}} \right)^2 \sigma_{in_i}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \tau_i}{\partial C_{out_i}} \right)^2 \sigma_{out_i}^2 \right) \quad (9)$$

The rate constants were then adjusted repeatedly, using a simplex search method [26] [27] [28] to find the best chi-square fit. The simplex method is computationally slow, but was chosen to ensure a true global minimum was found. A chi-square probability of less than 0.001 suggests that some assumption is wrong or needs to be challenged. For values less than 10^{-18} the hypothesis can be confidently rejected [29].

The chi-square fits for all the rate equations were massively rejected. Even a doubling of the ammonia determination uncertainty, yields chi-square probability many orders lower than 10^{-18} . Thus the reactions are indeed being influenced by film diffusion and or activators.

3.2. Confirmation of Plug Flow Behaviour

The long thin filters were designed to yield plug flow, but this was confirmed by a series of tracer studies on a filter, of identical construction to R1, at different flow rates. Deviations from ideal plug flow behaviour are described using the vessels dispersion number D/uL which characterizes the mixing in the axial direction. A pulse of NaCl solution was injected just upstream of the entrance with the water conductivity recorded after the exit. The contribution of the filter ends to the curves were removed in a numerical spline based version of the graphical method described by Levenspiel [30]. The dispersion number was obtained by fitting the data to Eqn. 10 [31], which is valid for small amounts of dispersion. A typical dimensionless C curve, after removing the end effects, at a flowrate of 10 min/l is given in Fig. 7.

$$C_\theta = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi D/uL}} \exp \left[-\frac{(1-\theta)^2}{4D/uL} \right] \quad (10)$$

Under all conditions the filter type shows small amounts of axial dispersion in line with literature values [30] for flow through packed beds.

In the case of small amounts of dispersion, as confirmed by the tracer studies, the difference in the conversion for any rate equation is given by [32]

Figure 7: Axial Dispersion

$$X^o - X = (D/uL)N_{out}^o \ln \left(\frac{N_{in}^o}{N_{out}^o} \right) \quad (11)$$

Based upon the Michaelis-Menten kinetic constants, for various flowrate groupings, the difference in the conversion is found to be an order of magnitude lower than the ammonia determination uncertainties.

3.3. Liquid Film Diffusion

The particle specific area, a , for the limestone chips was significantly larger than that for spheres with nitrite oxidising bacteria also occupying surface area. The amount of energy from nitrite oxidation is only a third of that from ammonia oxidation. It was thus assumed that the nitrite bacteria occupied a third of the area. The specific area of the ammonia oxidizing bacteria film, a_w , was taken as approximately that of a sphere of the same diameter as the chips. For the case that liquid film diffusion is influencing the reaction rate, the concentration C^* at the biofilm surface rather than that of the bulk liquid needs to be taken. The rate of reaction is equal to the rate of mass transfer, with a_w on both sides of the equation.

For Michaelis-Menten kinetics:

$$Na_w = a_w h(C - C^*) = \frac{a_w k_1 C^*}{1 + k_2 C^*} \quad (12)$$

The concentration at the biofilm surface, C^* , was calculated using a bisection method [26]. In the biological rate equation (BRE) diffusion within the biofilm is incorporated in the form of an effectiveness factor λ , itself a function of constants and the surface concentration. The constants $k_1 \dots k_2$ can be equated to parameters such as those in the biological rate equation (BRE), whereby they are not necessarily purely kinetic in nature. For the BRE $k_2 L$ is being fitted.

A large number of liquid film mass-transfer coefficient correlations were tested. Most literature correlations are for spheres and similar forms. Dwivedi and Upadhyay[33] give the following correlation for deep beds:

$$\varepsilon j_D = \frac{0.765}{Re^{0.82}} + \frac{0.365}{Re^{0.386}} \quad (13)$$

$$Sh = j_D Re Sc^{0.33} \quad (14)$$

$$h = \frac{Sh \mathcal{D}}{d_p} \quad (15)$$

The stated average standard deviation of this correlation is given at 17.95 %, which is thus considerably higher than the ammonia determination standard deviation of 4.8%. A standard deviation of 20% was used for the data analysis. The individual residence time uncertainty given in Eqn. 9 has to then include the partial derivative of the residence time with regard to the film coefficient. The diffusion coefficient at infinite dilution for ammonia was taken as $1.64 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ [34]. The value is for a temperature of 12°C rather than the rig water temperature of 15°C . The literature value given by Gujer [35] in his design procedure for trickling filters in waste treatment service at 15°C is $1.7 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

Based upon the ammonia oxidizing bacteria covering an area equivalent to that of spheres with the same diameter as the limestone chips, the initial analysis of the data [36] rejected liquid film mass-transfer outright. The analysis of these data sets was not followed up further at the time in order to do more laboratory based unsteady-state experiments.

3.4. Widening the Search for Liquid Film Mass-transfer Limitation

Despite the chi-probabilities being much less than 10^{-18} , the analysis has been extended by introducing a mass-transfer correction factor φ . It is looking for potential problems in the assumptions made.

$$Na_w = a_w \varphi h(C - C^*) = \frac{a_w k_1 C^*}{1 + k_2 C^*} \quad (16)$$

Stepping through values for the masstransfer correction, fits are indeed found albeit much lower than 1 and in a range corresponding to the uncertainties. The chi probability results, for all the rate equations, are shown in Fig. 8. The left hand plots are for A (—), B (⋯⋯), C (---) and H (----) kinetics as in Table. 2. The right hand plots are for D (—), E (⋯⋯), F (---) and I (----) kinetics. There were slight convergence difficulties with a few data points which have thus been omitted from the trends. The results using the older film transfer correlation of Chu et al [37] give the same results only with a broader spread. Outside the range the fits are massively rejected. The fits for Michaelis-Menten kinetics at the peak chi probability values and the associated error bars are shown in Fig. 9.

Depending upon the masstransfer correction factor the fitted kinetic constants vary. The results for filter R1 and R2 are in Table 3 for a masstransfer correction factor of 0.37 and 0.58 respectively.

Figure 8: Chi Probability of Liquid Film Mass Transfer

4. Discussion

The analysis was conducted using data from an operational submerged nitrification filter where the conditions are much in line with natural watercourses. The experiments here involved conducting a step change in flowrate 24 hours earlier, to a dynamic system that overall was at steady-state. The rigorous

Figure 9: Michaelis-Menten Kinetics and Liquid Film Diffusion

statistical analysis indicates that if mass transfer is neglected, all the kinetic equations derived for ammonia as a single substrate, under the given conditions, are rejected. Zero order kinetics is not compatible with film diffusion limiting the reaction.

With the introduction of the mass transfer correction factor excellent fits are obtained as given in Fig. 8, but at very much reduced liquid film mass transfer rates. Furthermore the correction factor for each of the filters, which were in parallel, is significantly different. Based upon the peak mass transfer correction probabilities, for each filter, the determined kinetic constant for commonly quoted kinetics differ greatly between the two filters. It could be thought that the lower mass transfer rates in R1 are being compensated by having more active enzyme sites with the use of activators, to give higher kinetic constants, but there is often several order of magnitude difference between the two. The literature mechanisms also do not have the use of activators in them. The more complicated BRE is no better than the simpler Michaelis-Menten kinetics equation and indicates that internal diffusion is not playing a large role, if any. Substrate inhibition although not rejected has very different constants for the two filters.

The remaining equations have constants that are close enough that the large use of an activator may not be required. Sigmoidal binding, half order kinetics and second order kinetics are all not rejected. The constants for sigmoidal bind-

Filter	R1 $\varphi = 0.37$				R2 $\varphi = 0.58$			
Eqn	Q	k_1	k_2	k_3 / n	Q	k_1	k_2	k_3 / n
A	1.0	12.72			1.000	6.2		
B	1.0	12.73	2.43		1.000	4.5	2.00	
C	0.985	15.71	4.89	12.02	1.000	5.16	1.53	7.72
D	0.977	5.76	1.99	11.63	0.998	223.74	142.21	409.02
E	1.0	0.89	0.33	0.81	1.000	1.18	0.36	0.91
F	0.998	44.51			1.000	37.96		
H	1.0	0.14			1.000	0.20		
I	0.995	3872			1.000	4480		

Table 3: Fitted Kinetic Constants

ing are similar for both R1 and R2, but it is for slightly negative cooperativity (with a non integer value). This scenario would have two molecules in which the second one is hindered by the binding of the first. A plot similar to the saturation/Michaelis-Menten plot can be made for a given sigmoidal binding order n . Half order kinetics arises from multiple step mechanisms with multiple molecules. With second order kinetics a bimolecular reaction mechanism is again envisaged.

The list of rate equation types has a notable exception, that of product inhibition. Hydroxylamine is highly mutagenic and it has been speculated that as a result it acts as an inhibitor. To test for product inhibition its concentration would need to be known. As hydroxylamine has never been detected during the normal oxidation of ammonia, it is never tested for in aquacultural systems. If hydroxylamine were to strongly inhibit the oxidation of ammonia it is debatable that the rate equations tested would give significant fits, but they do. The kinetic data presented here would concur with the conclusion that no to non measurable amounts of hydroxylamine were present. There are in fact many difficulties and objections to hydroxylamine itself as an intermediate. These are discussed in the following articles.

The ammonia molecule is small and has a high diffusivity. As such ammonia is an unlikely substrate to be associated with liquid film diffusion limitations. The fundamental problem, in a natural setting, is of very low substrate concentrations along with a membrane. How does a bacteria survive at such low substrate concentrations at the biofilm from a reaction that yields so little energy? Bacteria in suspension as a floc travelling at the same velocity as the water would be at a larger disadvantage still. An efficient control and optimization strategy is thus seen as an evolutionary must for nitrifying bacteria. To optimise the reactions it would be expected that the active area is maximized to counter the low film diffusion coefficients. That is the biofilm would be extremely thin and only bacteria on the surface would thrive. With liquid film diffusion playing a significant role a very strong evolutionary pressure to avoid internal diffusion limitation can be anticipated. Having binding molecules and

enzymes contained in the outer membranes would be a logical consequence to minimise diffusional limitations.

Filters taken out of service had a biofilm on all the surfaces. The experimental results however would have the active biofilm specific area or active filter length to be 60% or less than that anticipated in conjunction with liquid film diffusion. Biofilter R1 has only 37% of the anticipated mass transfer performance even though, based upon the tracer studies, it must have had good plug flow behaviour at start-up. Biofilter R2 with the conical entrance design and somewhat shorter length manages 58% of the anticipated performance. An alternative conclusion to the poor mass transfer performance findings in both cases is that the diffusion coefficient itself is around half the value for ammonia in water. The larger deviations in the fits tend to be at lower velocities and thus sloughing does not seem to have been a problem nor thus the experimental methodology where the flowrate was changed every 24 hours. Nitrification does yield hydrogen ions that move out into the bulk fluid. This could possibly slow the diffusion of the also positive ammonium ions, but the overall contribution is so low that this is not likely to be a significant effect.

Prehn [38] conducted experiments into the influence of liquid film diffusion on commercial pipe-mesh filter elements taken from a recycle aquaculture system. The experiments had the submerged filter elements in a recycle system acting as a batch reactor. Without liquid film correlations for the elements, in addition to the problems in defining characteristic lengths, direct comparison with the results here were thus not possible. They fitted their grouped data, where outliers were identified and removed, to zero order for a TAN between 3 and 1 mg/l and first order kinetics for TAN under 1 mg/l. The biofilm thickness was reported as 14 μm , so that mechanical stress issues should not be anticipated. For the first order fits they suggested that the low reaction rates were due to internal diffusion, but they did not test for this with BRE kinetics which encompasses internal diffusion.

If the filters contained significant amounts of heterotrophic bacteria then the ammonia reaction rate would involve two parallel reaction routes. The reaction kinetics would then be expected to be more complicated. It is doubted that the data could be fitted with such high probabilities if this was the case. Where present, heterotrophs could overgrow nitrifiers relatively easily as they have much more energy available by several orders of magnitude. For such low ammonia concentrations, as here and in natural watercourses, it would be extremely hard for nitrifiers to live under a significant inert biomass layer or under a heterotrophic biofilm [39]. Perhaps the nitrifying bacteria are not always in direct competition with heterotrophs, rather converting the toxic substrates and intermediates in a symbiosis with them. The nitrogen remains in a fixed form, but requires that heterotrophs expend more energy in a less toxic environment. Both sets of bacteria would benefit from higher fluid velocities that increase liquid film diffusion.

5. Conclusion

Nitrification has been examined from induced and natural perturbations to a recycle aquaculture system that received a constant nitrogen load over an extended period of time. Tracer experiments confirmed that the submerged nitrifying filters used were close to plug flow and axial dispersion effects can be excluded. With liquid film diffusion ignored all kinetics for ammonia as a single substrate are rejected. When liquid film diffusion is accounted for, using the diffusion coefficient for ammonia, the kinetics are once again rejected. The uncertainties involved in estimating a liquid film coefficient are much larger than those for the ammonia determination and might be expected to aid the chi fit, but this is not the case. Widening the analysis did indeed produce fits, but at much lower mass transfer rates than expected. This could imply a very much reduced active area in conjunction with liquid film diffusion, but the filters were observed to be covered in biofilm. Also a very thin film covering all the available area would be expected with liquid film diffusion limiting. An alternative explanation is that the diffusion coefficient is lower by at least a half.

Comparing the two filters kinetics, which were operated in parallel, half order kinetics is accepted. Cooperative behaviour is accepted too, albeit negative in nature. Second order kinetics is not rejected either and thus the corresponding bimolecular reaction mechanism. First order, Michaelis-Menten kinetics and the BRE are all accepted, but with the priory that there is a three fold differences in the numbers of active enzyme sites between the two filters that are in parallel.

To investigate the underlying reaction kinetics of nitrification liquid film mass-transfer as a variable, with its large uncertainties, has to be constrained. The kinetics and mechanisms can be better investigated with reduced mass-transfer complications by using a high fixed superficial velocity to particle diameter ratio. Potentially heterotrophic bacteria can, given a carbon source, compete with nitrifiers resulting in difficulties analysing the data. The kinetics are thus best examined using a recycle reactor design and using a medium solely for growing nitrifiers. The experiments here involve the reactions on an intermediate time scale, somewhat short for strategic optimization but too long for dynamic control. Studies involving perturbations much shorter than 24 hours were expected to reveal more.

Nomenclature

Symbols

A	Filter cross sectional area	m^2
a	Specific surface area	m^2/m^3
a_w	Active area of ammonia oxidizing bacteria per unit volume	m^2/m^3
C	Concentration of total ammonia nitrogen in bulk fluid	mg/l

C^*	Concentration of total ammonia nitrogen at biofilm	mg/l
D	Axial dispersion coefficient	m^2/s
d_p	Diameter of particle	m
h	Film Coefficient	m/s
j_D	Mass transfer factor	
$k_{1...3}$	Rate equation constants /coefficients (units depend upon equation)	
$k_{I...III}$	Apparent rate equation constants at fixed Re (units depend upon equation)	
L	Biofilm thickness	m
N	Rate of reaction for microbial film	$mg/l/min$
n	Rate order	
p	Number of data points	
Q	Probability of χ^2 exceeding a particular value by chance	
q	Flowrate	l/min
u	Superficial velocity	m/s
X	Conversion	
z	Filter length	m

Other Symbols

χ^2	Chi-square merit function	
λ	Effectiveness factor	
\mathcal{D}	Diffusion Coefficient	m^2/s
μ	Dynamic viscosity	Ns/m^2
ρ	Particle density	kg/m^3
σ	Standard deviation	
τ	Superficial residence time	min
θ	Dimensionless time	
ε	Voidage	
φ	MT correction	

Dimensionless Numbers

D/uL Dispersion number

$Re = \rho u d_p / \mu$ Reynolds number

$Sc = \mu / \rho D$ Schmidt number

$Sh = h d_p / D$ Sherwood number

Subscripts

Inlet Ammonia nitrogen concentration entering filter

Outlet Ammonia nitrogen concentration exiting filter

Superscripts

o Plug flow

References

- [1] P. B. Liao, R. D. Mayo, Salmonid hatchery water reuse systems, *Aquaculture* 1 (1972) 317–335.
- [2] S. Leininger, T. Urich, M. Schloter, L. Schwark, J. Qi, G. W. Nicol, J. I. Prosser, S. Schuster, C. Schleper, Archaea predominate among ammonia-oxidizing prokaryotes in soils, *Nature* 442 (7104) (2006) 806–809.
- [3] U. EPA”, Process design manual: Nitrogen control. Washington, DC: US environmental protection agency. report nr 625, Tech. rep., R-93/010 (1993).
- [4] F. Skinner, N. Walker, Growth of *Nitrosomonas europaea* in batch and continuous culture, *Archiv für Mikrobiologie* 38 (4) (1961) 339–349.
- [5] H. Donker, A. Kluyver, Die Einheit in der Biochemie, *Chem Zelle Gewebe* 13 (1926) 172.
- [6] H. Lees, Hydroxylamine as an intermediate in nitrification, *Nature* 169 (4291) (1952) 156–157.
- [7] T. Hofman, H. Lees, The biochemistry of the nitrifying organisms. 4. The respiration and intermediary metabolism of *Nitrosomonas*, *Biochemical Journal* 54 (4) (1953) 579–583.
- [8] C. Fewson, D. Nicholas, Utilization of nitrate by micro-organisms, *Nature* 190 (4770) (1961) 2–7.
- [9] M. Aleem, A. Nason, Metabolic pathways of bacterial nitrification, in: Symposium on marine microbiology, CC Thomas Springfield, Illinois, 1963, pp. 392–409.

- [10] B. Sharma, R. Ahlert, Nitrification and nitrogen removal, *Water Research* 11 (10) (1977) 897–925.
- [11] H. Painter, A review of literature on inorganic nitrogen metabolism in microorganisms, *Water Research* 4 (6) (1970) 393–450.
- [12] T. Yoshida, M. Alexander, Hydroxylamine formation by nitrosomonas europaea, *Canadian journal of microbiology* 10 (6) (1964) 923–926.
- [13] T. Yoshida, M. Alexander, Hydroxylamine oxidation by nitrosomonas europaea, *Soil Science* 111 (5) (1971) 307–312.
- [14] T. Hollocher, M. Tate, D. Nicholas, Oxidation of ammonia by nitrosomonas europaea. definite ^{18}O -tracer evidence that hydroxylamine formation involves a monooxygenase., *Journal of Biological chemistry* 256 (21) (1981) 10834–10836.
- [15] K. K. Andersson, A. B. Hooper, O_2 and H_2O are each the source of one O in NO_2^- produced from NH_3 by nitrosomonas: ^{15}N -NMR evidence, *FEBS Letters* 164 (2) (1983) 236–240.
- [16] H. Lees, Effect of copper-enzyme poisons on soil nitrification, *Nature* 158 (4003) (1946) 97–97.
- [17] P. Wood, Nitrification as a bacterial energy source, *Special Publications of the Society of General Microbiology*, Vol. 20: Nitrification (1986) 39–67.
- [18] C. C. Barford, J. P. Montoya, M. A. Altabet, R. Mitchell, Steady-state nitrogen isotope effects of N_2 and N_2O production in *Paracoccus denitrificans*, *Applied and environmental microbiology* 65 (3) (1999) 989–994.
- [19] N. Vajjala, W. Martens-Habbena, L. A. Sayavedra-Soto, A. Schauer, P. J. Bottomley, D. A. Stahl, D. J. Arp, Hydroxylamine as an intermediate in ammonia oxidation by globally abundant marine archaea, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110 (3) (2013) 1006–1011.
- [20] D. J. Arp, L. Y. Stein, Metabolism of inorganic N compounds by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria, *Critical Reviews in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 38 (6) (2003) 471–495.
- [21] J. D. H. Strickland, T. R. Parsons, *A practical handbook of seawater analysis*, Fisheries research board of Canada, 1972.
- [22] G. Knowles, A. L. Downing, M. Barrett, Determination of kinetic constants for nitrifying bacteria in mixed culture, with the aid of an electronic computer, *Microbiology* 38 (2) (1965) 263–278.
- [23] S. Zhu, S. Chen, The impact of temperature on nitrification rate in fixed film biofilters, *Aquacultural Engineering* 26 (4) (2002) 221–237.

- [24] B. Atkinson, I. Daoud, The analogy between micro-biological reactions and heterogeneous catalysis, *Trans. Inst. Chem. Eng* 46 (1968) "T19–T24".
- [25] R. T. Haug, P. L. McCarty, Nitrification with submerged filters, *Journal (Water Pollution Control Federation)* (1972) 2086–2102.
- [26] W. H. Press, B. P. Flannery, S. A. Teukolsky, W. T. Vetterling, *Numerical Recipes in Pascal: The Art of Scientific Computing* [disc], Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- [27] J. A. Nelder, R. Mead, A simplex method for function minimization, *The computer journal* 7 (4) (1965) 308–313.
- [28] B. D. Bunday, *Basic optimisation methods*, Edward Arnold London, 1984.
- [29] W. H. Press, B. P. Flannery, S. A. Teukolsky, W. T. Vetterling, *Numerical Recipes in Pascal: The Art of Scientific Computing* [disc], Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- [30] O. Levenspiel, *Chemical reaction engineering*, John Wiley & Sons, 1972.
- [31] O. Levenspiel, W. Smith, Notes on the diffusion-type model for the longitudinal mixing of fluids in flow, *Chemical Engineering Science* 6 (4-5) (1957) 227–235.
- [32] I. Pasquon, M. Dente, Heat and mass transfer in methanol synthesis—optimum operating conditions of the reactors, *Journal of Catalysis* 1 (6) (1962) 508–520.
- [33] P. N. Dwivedi, S. N. Upadhyay, Particle-fluid mass transfer in fixed and fluidized beds, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Process Design and Development* 16 (2) (1977) 157–165.
- [34] R. C. Reid, J. M. Prausnitz, B. E. Poling, *The properties of gases and liquids*, McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, NY, 1987, table 11-4.
- [35] W. Gujer, M. Boller, Design of a nitrifying tertiary trickling filter based on theoretical concepts, *Water Research* 20 (11) (1986) 1353–1362.
- [36] A. P. G. Newton, Investigations into the kinetics of nitrification, Ph.D. thesis, Department of Chemical and Process Engineering, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, UK (9 1990).
- [37] J. Chu, J. Kalil, A. Wetteroth, mass transfer in a fluidized bed, *Chemical Engineering Progress* 49 (3) (1953) 141–149.
- [38] J. Prehn, C. K. Waul, L.-F. Pedersen, E. Arvin, Impact of water boundary layer diffusion on the nitrification rate of submerged biofilter elements from a recirculating aquaculture system, *Water research* 46 (11) (2012) 3516–3524.

- [39] B. E. Rittmann, J. A. Manem, Development and experimental evaluation of a steady-state, multispecies biofilm model, *Biotechnology and bioengineering* 39 (9) (1992) 914–922.